

New “ONE-STEP” Thiol Functionalization Procedure for Ni by Self-Assembled Monolayers

Claudio Fontanesi^{a*}, Francesco Tassinari^a, Francesca Parenti^a, Hagai Cohen^b, Prakash Chandra Mondal^c, Vankayala Kiran^c, Angelo Giglia^d, Luca Pasquali^{d,e,f}, and Ron Naaman^{c*}

^aDSCG, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Via Campi 183, Modena-41125

^bDepartment of Chemical Research Support, The Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot-76100,
Israel

^cDepartment of Chemical Physics, The Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot-76100 Israel

^dCNR - Istituto Officina dei Materiali, S.S. 14, km 163.5 in Area Science Park, I-34012 Trieste,
Italy

^eDipartimento di Ingegneria “Enzo Ferrari”, Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia, Via Vignolese
905, Modena-41125, Italy

^fDepartment of Physics, University of Johannesburg, PO Box 524, Auckland Park, 2006, South
Africa

ABSTRACT

This paper reports on a facile and fast strategy for Self-Assembled Monolayer (SAM) functionalization of nickel surfaces, employing cyclic voltammetry (CV) cycling of a suitable tailored solution containing the species to be adsorbed. Results are presented for ultrathin films formed on Ni by 1-hexadecanethiol (C16), L-cysteine (L-cys) and the poly{methyl (2R)-3-(2,2'-bithiophen-4-ylsulfanyl)-2-[(tert-butoxycarbonyl)amino]propanoate} (PCT-L) thiophene based polymer. The effective formation of high-quality ultrathin organic films on the nickel was verified

both electrochemically, and by exploiting typical surface characterization techniques, such as contact angle, ellipsometry, atomic force microscopy (AFM), polarization modulation-infrared reflection-absorption spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

KEYWORDS: Self-assembled monolayer, base metals, electrochemical reduction, nickel, ferromagnetic material

1. INTRODUCTION

Self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) chemisorbed on solid surfaces have been extensively studied owing to their potential technical applications and their contribution to our basic understanding of surface and interfacial properties.¹ Most of these studies focus on self-assembly of thiols on gold² and much less on other possible substrate/adsorbate combinations. Base metals (e.g., nickel, iron, cobalt, and silver³) are known to quickly form a surface oxide layer under ambient conditions, making molecular controlled functionalization through self-assembly difficult, unless a multistep procedure is used.⁴⁻⁷ One of the obvious applications of SAMs, adsorbed on non-noble metals, is the protection of the surface from corrosion. Closely packed organized monolayers can hinder the diffusion of oxidizing species to the surface and can block the dissolution of the metals. Other significant applications range from hydrophobic coatings⁵ to surface lubricants.³ The extensive use of these metals in industry and their interesting applications provide motivation to develop new, simpler, and more robust procedures for applying the self-assembly techniques to these materials. The present study focuses on ferromagnetic nickel, since it has unique magnetic properties that are having both of high scientific and technological interest.^{8,9} An original one-step procedure is presented, which is based on applying repetitive cyclic voltammetry electro-reduction consecutive cycles of the nickel surface in a suitable solution containing the organic compound to be chemi-adsorbed on the metallic Ni. The nickel surface is functionalized as soon as it becomes oxide free and the subsequent potential cycling works as electrochemical annealing, improving the order of the film. Our electrochemical based method takes advantage of multiple simultaneous favorable conditions: i) the reduction of the NiO_x surface to metallic nickel, ii) the prevention of oxide-layer formation, iii) concomitant chemisorption of thiol on Ni, and iv) the repetitive CV cycling that significantly improves the alignment of the alkyl chains owing to the applied electric field/adsorbed-molecule dipole moment interaction¹⁰. Moreover, it is a highly flexible procedure: there are no acidic/basic environment restrictions, no limitations on the thiol solubility, and no

particular handling of the electrodes (e.g., emersion, washing) is required. Possible use of both acidic/basic environment, selection of a suitable solvent or a mixture of solvents, no limitations on the organic concentration, no particular need for pretreating the electrodes (e.g., emersion, washing), and the easy possible tuning of the experimental conditions (so that the procedure can be used with other metals) constitute the major advantages present in our new procedure, when compared to other methods previously reported in the literature.¹¹

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Reagents

All reagents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used without further purification. 300 nm-thick Ni (CERAC, 99.9995%) was evaporated on a 5 nm Ti (Kurt, 99.9%) adhesion layer supported on 0.3 mm-thick microscope cover slips (Gerhard Menzel GmbH). The poly{methyl (2R)-3-(2,2'-bithiophen-4-ylsulfanyl)-2-[(tert-butoxycarbonyl)amino]propanoate} thiophene based polymer (PCT-L) is from original synthesis, compare the Supporting Information for the details on the synthesis and product characterization; the PCT-L structure is shown in Chart 1.

Chart 1: Monomeric structure of poly{methyl (2R)-3-(2,2'-bithiophen-4-ylsulfanyl)-2-[(tert-butoxycarbonyl)amino]propanoate} thiophene.

Electrochemical Measurements. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were performed using an Autolab PGSTAT 20 potentiostat and by employing a typical three-electrode electrochemical cell

arrangement. Evaporated Ni surfaces, a Pt wire, and an Ag/AgCl/KCl_{sat} electrode were used as the working, counter, and reference electrodes, respectively.

Ellipsometry. The thickness of the SAM was measured using a multiple wavelength ellipsometer (M 2000 V from J. A. Woollam Co., Inc.) at a constant incidence angle of 70° under ambient conditions and was analyzed using commercial software (WVASE32).

Vibrational spectroscopy. Infrared spectra were recorded in polarization modulation-infrared reflection-absorption mode, PM-IRRAS, using a Nicolet 6700 FTIR, at an 80° incidence angle, equipped with a PEM-90 photoelastic modulator (Hinds Instruments, Hillsboro, OR).

Static Contact Angle. Contact angle (CA) measurements were performed with an automated goniometer (Rame-Hart, model-100), and micro syringe droplets (advancing drop method) of approximately 4 μL deionized water (Millipore, Inc.). Contact angle data were recorded immediately after Ni functionalization.

AFM Imaging. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were obtained using Multimode/Nanoscope (Bruker-Nano, Santa Barbara, CA, USA). Images were acquired in non-contact mode and a Si probe was used whose resonance frequency was 70-90 kHz. The topographical images were taken at a scan rate of 0.5 Hz. Several images were taken in different fields of view (0.5-2.0 μm) to ensure uniformity and reproducibility.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

1-hexadecanethiol

XPS measurements were performed using a Kratos AXIS ULTRA DLD spectrometer, with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) at 75 W. Several take-off angles were used at detection pass energies ranging between 10 and 80 eV. Freshly prepared samples were inserted into the sample chamber. Composition and thickness analyses were deduced from both the relative intensities of Ni3p and Ni2p, as well as their comparison with the O1s, C1s, and S2p line intensities. Argon ion sputtering at 4 keV was further applied as a complementary tool for depth profiling. Curve fitting with Gaussian Lorentzian line shapes was used for decomposing different

species contributing to a given elemental line. Atomic concentration ratios were translated to layer thickness, assuming first that a uniform organic layer is on top of a perfect, planar oxide layer on an infinite metal substrate. In a second step, these values were improved by considering two types of imperfections: surface roughness and incomplete coverage of both the oxide and the SAM on the metal.

PCT-L polymer. XPS measurements for PCT-L polymer coated samples were performed at the BEAR beamline at Elettra synchrotron radiation facility.¹² Photoemission was taken at normal emission with the light impinging at 45° with respect to the surface normal and at different photon energy in the range 100-1000 eV with an hemispherical analyzer – 66 mm mean radius. Overall energy resolution (analyzer and monochromator) was 0.1-0.5 eV, depending on the photon energy. The emission lines from Au 4f levels of a gold reference sample were acquired at each photon energy and were taken as an energy reference with Au 4f_{7/2} = 84.0 eV. The spectra are here presented after a Shirley background subtraction.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 *Electrochemistry.* Freshly evaporated nickel substrates were cleaned in boiling acetone, followed by ethanol for 10 min each and then dried under an N₂ stream before performing electrochemical reduction in an N₂-filled glove box (O₂ < 5 ppm). The 1-hexadecanethiol and L-cysteine SAM functionalization was carried out in a mixed water/ethanol solvent under a reduction potential regime, which was followed by electrochemical annealing. The reduction regime allows for the reduction of the initial NiO_x on the surface and prevents the subsequent nickel oxidation; simultaneously, SAM formation occurs. Figure 1a shows the repetitive potential cycling of the Ni surface in 4 mM 1-hexadecanethiol, 0.05 M Na₂SO₄-based electrolyte, in water/ethanol (0.8:1, v/v) solvent, pH < 4 (obtained by adding dil. H₂SO₄).

Figure 1: a) Current vs voltage graph, 10 subsequent CV cycles ($E_{ini} = -0.1$ V, $E_{inversion} = -1.0$ V), with a scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} . Solution composition: 4 mM 1-hexadecanethiol, 0.05 M Na_2SO_4 , water/ethanol (0.8:1, v/v) solvent, pH < 4. b) CVs of a 5 mM $K_3Fe(CN)_6/K_4Fe(CN)_6$ aqueous solution, 0.3 M K_2SO_4 as the base electrolyte, and with a 0.05 V s^{-1} scan rate. The black line indicates the pristine Ni substrate, whereas the red line indicates a functionalized Ni substrate.

In the first CV cycle a broad peak is found at about -0.9 V, assigned the reduction of the nickel oxide on the surface.¹³ The electrochemical reduction procedure consists of 15 subsequent CV cycles with an initial potential $E_{ini} = -0.1$ V, a second vertex potential $E_{inversion} = -1.0$ V at scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} . Upon increasing the number of cycles, the reduction current, at -1.0 V, decreases. This result clearly indicates the progressive surface coverage and well-packed SAM formation by 1-hexadecanethiol. The formation of the monolayer was also confirmed by cyclic voltammetry. For instance, Figure 1b shows CVs of the modified Ni-electrode in a 5 mM $K_3Fe(CN)_6/K_4Fe(CN)_6$ aqueous solution containing 0.3 M K_2SO_4 as the base electrolyte and at a scan rate of 0.05 V s^{-1} . The decrease in the current density (red curve) of the modified Ni as compared to the unmodified Ni electrode (black curve) is a clear indication of the passivation of the Ni. The polymer was also assembled on nickel using the same methodology. Figure S1 shows the repetitive potential cycling

of the Ni surface in 0.5 mM PCT-L polymer containing 0.1M tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TBATFB) in chloroform. A broad shoulder, centered at about -0.75 V, is found in the first scan corresponding at the reduction of the nickel oxide, note that after the fifth potential cycle the current drops almost to zero.

A quite similar procedure was used to form an L-cysteine SAM on nickel. L-cysteine monolayer was selected since its adsorption results in a SAM containing a free carboxylic group facing the solution, which can be further extended to make an amide bond using a primary amine (*vide infra*).

3.2 Contact Angle. The static water contact angle measurements of freshly prepared Ni substrates, 1-hexadecanethiol coated Ni and L-cysteine -terminated Ni substrates are $52 \pm 2^\circ$, $106 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and $22 \pm 0.5^\circ$, respectively, confirming well-organized SAM formation by the organic molecules.

3.3 Ellipsometry measurement. The thickness of the SAM, measured by ellipsometry, is found at 1.8 nm, indicating the attachment of the 1-hexadecanethiol onto the Ni-substrate. Ellipsometry-derived polymer film thickness of Ni-Polymer was estimated as 20 ± 2 Å. Notably, the optimized length of the polymer was calculated at ≈ 30 Å. This result shows that the polymer on surfaces is not standing strictly upright, rather, it is tilted by 40° with respect to the surface normal.

Covalent grafting of TBO on Ni/L-Cysteine. L-cysteine SAM was employed to covalent grafting with toluidine blue O (TBO). To achieve such an assembly fabrication, TBO was chosen, since it is a redox probe well suited to fit the (rather narrow) double layer potential window of nickel, as well as to carry an amino moiety. The fabrication of the hybrid Ni/L-cysteine/TBO interface is carried out via two-step process (see **Scheme 1**). First, L-cysteine SAM formation was carried out following our procedure as mentioned above. Then, the covalent grafting of TBO on the Ni/L-cysteine surface was performed using an EDC/NHS solution¹⁴: the Ni/L-cysteine SAM was placed into a solution of EDC/NHS¹ (in 10 mM phosphate buffer, pH = 7) for 45 min (within an N₂-filled glove box); then the surface was cleaned properly using the same buffer solution. Then it was

¹ EDC stands for N-Ethyl-N'-(3-(dimethylamino)-propyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride, and NHS stands for N-Hydroxysuccinimide

dipped into a 0.1 mM TBO solution for 2 h. Subsequently, the sample was rinsed with the same buffer solution and dried properly under N₂ before CV measurements. Figure 2a shows CVs of the toluidine blue-O redox couple grafted to Ni through an L-cysteine SAM, Ni/L-Cysteine/TBO.

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of L-cysteine SAM formation on Ni. Formation of the amide bond was carried out using TBO in the presence of EDC/NHS in phosphate buffer at pH 7.

The Ni/L-cysteine did not show any redox peak in CVs recorded in the -0.25 to 0.15 V potential range (see Fig. S2), whereas the hybrid Ni/L-Cysteine/TBO interface shows a quasi-reversible pattern (Fig. 2a): reduction/oxidation peaks feature a peak-to-peak potential separation of about 0.03 V at a scanning rate of 0.05 V s⁻¹, in good agreement with the results obtained on a gold substrate, compare the relevant CV the Supporting Info (Fig. S3) and results reported by Nasri et al.¹⁵ The current densities (I_{pa} & I_{pc}) of the Ni/L-Cysteine/TBO-system exhibit an excellent linear dependence ($R^2 > 0.97$) on the scan rate (v); Fig. 2b reveals a diffusion-less electrochemical process¹⁶. Furthermore, the plot of the ratio of peak current densities vs the scan rate shows the unit value, thus indicating a reversible redox process for the adsorbed species.

Figure 2. a) Cyclic voltammogram of the Ni/L-cysteine/TBO interface (as working electrode) in 10 mM phosphate buffer containing 0.1 M KCl water solution, pH =7. The scan rate used was 0.1 V s⁻¹. b) The plot of current densities of the anodic and cathodic peaks, I_{pa} and I_{pc} , respectively, as a function of the scan rate (v). Inset shows plot of ratio of anodic current to cathodic current as a function of scan rate (I_{pa}/I_{pc} vs v).

3.2 PM-IRRAS

Figure 3 shows experimental PM-IRRAS spectra of both the Ni/1-hexadecanethiol and Ni/L-cysteine hybrid interfaces, following the electrochemically assisted functionalization. Figure 4a shows the 2750–3150 cm⁻¹ range, relevant to the C–H stretching frequency of the –CH₂ groups. Three prominent peaks are present at 2963, 2920, 2851 cm⁻¹, and are ascribed as ν_{as} (–CH₃), ν_{as} (–CH₂), and ν_s (–CH₂), respectively, which are consistent with the published data.^{17,18} Remarkably, a minor peak at 2877 cm⁻¹ is present which is rarely recorded in PM-IRRAS spectra, the latter is attributed to alkyl thiol SAM of extremely good quality.¹⁹ This result is consistent with the formation of a closed packed SAM with the molecules adsorbed in an upright orientation, which compares well to similar results obtained, for instance, by Sadler et al.¹⁸ The peak observed at 1713 and 1643 cm⁻¹ is due to the carbonyl (C=O) stretching frequency in the carboxylic group and N-H

bending in NH_2 present in the cysteine monolayer (Figure 3b). This observation revealed the formation of ordered monolayer on Ni surface.

Figure 3. PM-IRRAS spectra of 1-hexadecanethiol SAM on Ni in 2750–3150 cm^{-1} range (a), and L-cysteine SAM on Ni in 1450–1800 cm^{-1} range (b).

Figure 4. PM-IRRAS spectra of PCT-L on the Ni electrode: a) low wavelength range. b) high wavelength range.

Figure 4 sets out PM-IRRAS spectra of the Ni surface after our electrochemical driven functionalization. Figure 5a is characterized by the presence of a prominent peak found at 1721 cm^{-1}

which is due to the carbonyl group, whereas Figure 4b features the pattern typical of the methyl C–H stretching modes, even if the main peak is found at 2925 cm^{-1} , indicating a liquid-like organization of the side chains (on the other hand the adsorbed polymer arrangement is not expected to yield a close packing of the aliphatic chains).

3.3 AFM

Several images were taken at different fields of view ($0.5\text{--}2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$) to probe the uniformity and reproducibility of the SAM formed. The roughness values, R_q , were obtained from $2\text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ images (Fig. 5). For bare nickel substrates, the R_q values were found to be $2.5 \pm 0.4\text{ nm}$, whereas the value for L-Cysteine SAM on a Nickel substrate is around $1.3 \pm 0.1\text{ nm}$. This indicates that our electrochemical procedure does not induce a dramatic roughening of the electrode surface. By and large, the small, even if not negligible, decrease in R_q values, measured after the electrochemical treatment, can be attributed to the flexibility of organic molecules that are adsorbed on the nickel surface, which somehow can mask/smooth the discontinuities of the nickel solid substrate.

Figure 5. Tapping mode AFM images; the scan area was $2.0\text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 2.0\text{ }\mu\text{m}$: a) bare Ni ($R_q = 2.5\text{ nm}$); b) Ni/L-Cysteine ($R_q = 1.3\text{ nm}$) (right panel).

3.3 XPS

3.3.1 1-Hexadecanethiol

XPS elemental spectra of pristine nickel and SAM made from 1-Hexadecanethiol on nickel are shown in Figure 6. Table 1 (Supporting Information) summarizes the relevant atomic concentrations (%). The substrate oxidation is evident from the Ni 2p_{3/2} (854.3 eV) and O 1s (529.6 eV) peaks (See Figure 6 a, b), whereas metallic Ni shows up at 852.7 eV and is common to both the reference and treated samples. At least two additional peaks corresponding to Ni(OH)₂ and Ni₂O₃, perhaps also Ni(RCOO)₂, appear as overlapping components at 856.4 eV (the Ni signal) and 531.7 eV (the O signal). The NiS signal should appear at 852.8 eV, which is unresolved from the metallic Ni line. Quantification of the above substrate's components, combined with both angle-dependent XPS and Ar-sputtering results (not shown), led to the conclusion that after the electrochemical treatment the Ni is largely reduced, so that most of the surface oxide is removed. Figures 6 c and d display C 1s and S 2p spectra, respectively, show that a negligible amount of oxidized C and oxidized S is present on the surface after the electrochemical treatment. Note that for a perfectly ordered full coverage, and on a smooth planar substrate, one would expect $d_c=20.2 \text{ \AA}$ value for the 1-Hexadecanethiol film thickness, together with a carbon-to-sulfur ratio of C/S=16. Assuming for the attenuation of photoelectrons a discrete set of atomic layers, as described previously,²⁰ a d_c value of 25 \AA is obtained from elaboration of the experimental spectra, and a C/S ratio of 11.5 (see Supporting Information Table I for details). Thus, the following conclusions can be inferred from the XPS data: 1) surface roughness, even if present, appears as a minor consequence of the electrochemical treatment, 2) the Ni-oxide species are probably located at the non-covered domains (possibly deriving from oxygen contamination present in the pristine Ni) together with the extra S signal (the latter being mainly NiS, and to a lesser extent oxidized S), which should result in a non-conductive and reactive surface, 3) upon SAM formation, an extra thickness of about 2 nm is added with respect to the pristine Ni surface. In addition, there is a substantial increase in the sulfur and

carbon concentrations, and the oxidation state of the sulfur on the electrochemically functionalized Ni surface is indicative of a reduced electronic state (a peak found at 162.3 eV), strongly suggesting the occurring of a covalent Ni-S interaction. As a whole, the XPS results prove the formation of an ultra-thin film of 1-Hexadecanethiol SAM (ranging between one to two monolayers), a result consistent with the ellipsometry data.

Figure 6. Ni 2p (a), O 1s (b), C 1s (c), and S 2p (d) XP spectra of pristine Ni (red) and functionalized Ni using 1-hexadecanethiol (blue).

3.3.2 PCT-L chiral polymer.

Figure 7a shows Ni 2p spectra for the nickel with the self-assembled polymer monolayer on it. The spectrum line shape (no background subtraction was applied in this case) and the structure at 853.4 eV of Ni 2p_{3/2} indicates the presence of NiO at the surface of the electrode.²¹ The structure at 871.9 eV is consistent with the energy of the Ni 2p_{1/2} of NiO, confirming this attribution.²² The satellites of

both peaks are also visible. Figure 7b shows the S 2p spectra of the same sample. The spectrum has been deconvoluted in three different doublet peaks, taking into account the spin-orbit splitting of S $2p_{3/2}$ -S $2p_{1/2}$ components of 1.2 eV and their branching ratio of 2:1. The main peak at 163.5 eV is associated to sulfur in the thiophene rings – or to unbound S, while the one at 161.0 eV gives a strong indication of the presence of some level of reaction between S and the substrate, with the formation possible molecular fragments from reacted thiophene units and chemisorbed sulfur.²³ The bonding between S in the cysteine groups with the substrate can also contribute to the low binding energy feature.³ The third and less intense peak observed at 168.0 eV confirms the presence of a small amount of oxidized sulfur.²³ These three structures are well consistent with the overall picture of the monolayer structure, with some thiophenic sulfurs or cysteine S terminals that interact strongly with the surface. The presence of some oxidized sulfur can be explained by taking into account the relative fragility of the side chain cysteine Boc protected moiety (See Chart 1), which can undergo oxidation reactions. Looking at the O 1s spectra (Figure 7c), the structure of the signal can be deconvoluted in 3 main peaks: the one at 531.4 eV, and a second one at 529.6 eV, they are assigned to oxygen in NiO at the surface of the electrode,²⁴ whereas the smaller peak at 532.8 eV is found to be at the typical energy of a carbonyl oxygen of the cysteine aminoacid.²⁵ In figure 7d the N 1s spectra shows a single at 398.2 eV: the only nitrogen present in the polymer is in the amide group of the side chain protected aminoacid, and the energy value is perfectly compatible with such attribution.²⁵ In figure 7e the C 1s spectra is reported. The main feature is a peak at 284.8 eV with a broad tail towards higher binding energy, giving rise to the second peak feature in the deconvolution. This main asymmetric structure is assigned to carbon atoms in the thiophene rings or C not bound to heteroatoms: this is the energy where we expect to find most of the carbon atoms of the polymer.²⁶ The small contribution at 288.5 eV is associated to some level of oxidation and to a shake-up satellite. XPS results suggest that the thin polymeric layer is chemisorbed on the Ni surface. Some levels of strong chemical reactions are observed between S and the substrate, leading to charge transfer and possibly some degree of fragmentation of the polymeric backbone. The

substrate surface appears partially oxidized, which can be expected due to the high reactivity of clean Ni during the film deposition steps and subsequent exposure to air.

Figure 7. Selected XPS lines of PCT-L thiophene-polymer functionalized Ni in the binding energy region of Ni 2p (a), and S 2p (b) O 1s (c), N 2p (d), and C 1s (e).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The formation of high-quality ultra-thin organic films chemisorbed on Ni has been verified and characterized by exploiting different and independent surface-sensitive methods. Contact angle, PM-IRRAS, ellipsometry, AFM results yield a consistent picture indicating the effective chemisorption/formation and good ordering of the organics on the Ni surface. XPS outcome demonstrates that the formation of a Ni-S covalent chemical bond is involved in the adsorbate/substrate interaction. The application of the electrochemically assisted functionalization procedure results in two important outcomes:

1) Successful grafting of the TBO redox probe to Ni, exploiting L-cysteine SAM as the linker. CV plots verify the existence of the Ni/L-cysteine/TBO hybrid interface. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report showing successful grafting of a redox probe to Ni through a thiol SAM.

2) Our procedure allowed for the chemisorption of a cysteine or thiophene based polymer on Ni. The Ni-polymer and Ni-L-cysteine interfaces have been exploited to build a magnetoresistance device.^{26,27}

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Cyclic voltammograms and characterization data of L-polymer (Fig. S1-S7). This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

*E-mail: claudio.fontanesi@unimore.it (C.F).

*E-mail: ron.naaman@weizmann.ac.il (R.N).

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

RN acknowledges the partial support of the Israel Science Foundation and an ERC-Adv grant. CF acknowledges the ELETTRA/BEAR synchrotron facility support: proposal 20140070. Prof. Stefano Nannarone is acknowledged for helpful scientific discussion.

REFERENCES

- (1) Ulman, A. *An Introduction to Ultrathin Organic Films*, 1st Edition, Academic Press, Boston, 1991.
- (2) Bain, C. D.; Troughton, E. B.; Tao, Y. T.; Evall, J.; Whitesides, G. M.; Nuzzo, R. G. Formation of Monolayer Films by the Spontaneous Assembly of Organic Thiols from Solution onto Gold. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1989**, *111*, 321–335.
- (3) Kumar, K. S.; Naaman, R. Quantitative Analysis and Characterization of Self-Assembled DNA on a Silver Surface. *Langmuir* **2012**, *28*, 14514–14517.
- (4) Noel, S.; Houze, F.; Boyer, L.; Mekhalif, Z.; Caudano, R.; Delhalle, J. Self-Assembled Monolayers of Alkanethiols on Nickel Surfaces for Low Level Electrical Contact Applications. In *Proceedings of the Forty-Third IEEE Holm Conference on Electrical Contacts*, 1997; 1997; pp. 212–218.
- (5) Tortech, L.; Mekhalif, Z.; Delhalle, J.; Guittard, F.; Geribaldi, S. Self-Assembled Monolayers of Semifluorinated Thiols on Electrochemically Modified Polycrystalline Nickel Surfaces. *Thin Solid Films* **2005**, *491*, 253–259.
- (6) Rajalingam, S.; Devillers, S.; Dehalle, J.; Mekhalif, Z. A Two Step Process to Form Organothiol Self-Assembled Monolayers on Nickel Surfaces. *Thin Solid Films* **2012**, *522*, 247–253.
- (7) Mekhalif, Z.; Riga, J.; Pireaux, J.-J.; Delhalle, J. Self-Assembled Monolayers of N-Dodecanethiol on Electrochemically Modified Polycrystalline Nickel Surfaces. *Langmuir* **1997**, *13*, 2285–2290.
- (8) Organic Spintronics <http://www.organic-spintronics.com/index.php?sel=h1> (accessed May 31, 2014).
- (9) Naaman, R.; Waldeck, D. H. Chiral-Induced Spin Selectivity Effect. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2012**, *3*, 2178–2187.
- (10) Petrovic, .; Metiko-Hukovic, M.; Harvey, J.; Omanovic, S. Enhancement of Structural and Charge-Transfer Barrier Properties of N-Alkanethiol Layers on a Polycrystalline Copper Surface by Electrochemical Potentiodynamic Polarization. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2010**, *12*, 6590.
- (11) Bengio, S.; Fonticelli, M.; Benitez, G.; Creus, A. H.; Carro, P.; Ascolani, H.; Zampieri, G.; Blum, B.; Salvarezza, R. C. Electrochemical Self-Assembly of Alkanethiolate Molecules on Ni(111) and Polycrystalline Ni Surfaces. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2005**, *109*, 23450–23460.
- (12) Nannarone, S.; Borgatti, F.; DeLuisa, A.; Doyle, B. P.; Gazzadi, G. C.; Giglia, A.; Finetti, P.; Mahne, N.; Pasquali, L.; Pedio, M.; et al. The BEAR Beamline at Elettra. In *AIP Conference Proceedings*; AIP Publishing, 2004; Vol. 705, pp. 450–453.
- (13) Suzuki, T.; Yamada, T.; Itaya, K. In Situ Electrochemical Scanning Tunneling Microscopy of Ni(111), Ni(100), and Sulfur-Modified Ni(100) in Acidic Solution. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1996**, *100*, 8954–8961.

- (14) Slinker, J. D.; Muren, N. B.; Renfrew, S. E.; Barton, J. K. DNA Charge Transport over 34 Nm. *Nat. Chem.* **2011**, *3*, 230–235.
- (15) Nasri, Z.; Shams, E.; Ahmadi, M. Direct Modification of a Glassy Carbon Electrode with Toluidine Blue Diazonium Salt: Application to NADH Determination and Biosensing of Ethanol. *Electroanalysis* **2013**, *25*, 1917–1925.
- (16) Eckermann, A. L.; Feld, D. J.; Shaw, J. A.; Meade, T. J. Electrochemistry of Redox-Active Self-Assembled Monolayers. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2010**, *254*, 1769–1802.
- (17) Kim, C.-K.; Marshall, G. M.; Martin, M.; Bisson-Viens, M.; Wasilewski, Z.; Dubowski, J. J. Formation Dynamics of Hexadecanethiol Self-Assembled Monolayers on (001) GaAs Observed with Photoluminescence and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopies. *J. Appl. Phys.* **2009**, *106*, 083518.
- (18) Sadler, J. E.; Szumski, D. S.; Kierzkowska, A.; Catarelli, S. R.; Stella, K.; Nichols, R. J.; Fonticelli, M. H.; Benitez, G.; Blum, B.; Salvarezza, R. C.; et al. Surface Functionalization of Electro-Deposited Nickel. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2011**, *13*, 17987–17993.
- (19) Frey, B. L.; Corn, R. M.; Weibel, S. C. Polarization-Modulation Approaches to Reflection–Absorption Spectroscopy. In *Handbook of Vibrational Spectroscopy*; John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2006.
- (20) Wen, K.; Maoz, R.; Cohen, H.; Sagiv, J.; Gibaud, A.; Desert, A.; Ocko, B. M. Postassembly Chemical Modification of a Highly Ordered Organosilane Multilayer: New Insights into the Structure, Bonding, and Dynamics of Self-Assembling Silane Monolayers. *ACS Nano* **2008**, *2*, 579–599.
- (21) Briggs, D. Handbook of X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy C. D. Wanger, W. M. Riggs, L. E. Davis, J. F. Moulder and G. E. Muilenberg Perkin-Elmer Corp., Physical Electronics Division, Eden Prairie, Minnesota, USA, 1979. 190 Pp. \$195. *Surf. Interface Anal.* **1981**, *3*, v – v.
- (22) Mansour, A. N. Characterization of NiO by XPS. *Surf. Sci. Spectra* **1994**, *3*, 231.
- (23) Samba, R. Is the Enhanced Adhesion of PEDOT Thin Films on Electrodes Due to Sulfur - Gold Interaction? - An XPS Study. *Open Surf. Sci. J.* **2013**, *5*, 17–20.
- (24) McIntyre, N. S.; Cook, M. G. X-Ray Photoelectron Studies on Some Oxides and Hydroxides of Cobalt, Nickel, and Copper. *Anal. Chem.* **1975**, *47*, 2208–2213.
- (25) Wolak, M. The Electronic Structure of Biomolecular SelfAssembled Monolayers.
- (26) Lachkar, A.; Selmani, A.; Sacher, E. Metallization of Polythiophenes II. Interaction of Vapor-Deposited Cr, V and Ti with poly(3-Hexylthiophene) (P3HT). *Synth. Met.* **1995**, *72*, 73–80.
- (26) Mondal, P. C.; Kantor-Uriel, N.; Mathew, S. P.; Tassinari, F.; Fontanesi, C.; Naaman, R. Chiral Conductive Polymers as Spin Filters. *Adv. Mat.* **2015**, (in press).
- (27) Mathew, S. P.; Mondal, P. C.; Moshe, H.; Mastai, Y.; Naaman, R. Non-magnetic Organic/Inorganic Spin Injector at Room Temperature. *App. Phys. Lett.* **2014**, *105*, 242408.